

The study of [4+2] cycloaddition reactions of some unactivated aldehydes with a simple diene : Role of various iron(III) porphyrins as catalysts[†]

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Abstract : The [4+2] hetero Diels-Alder reaction of some benzaldehyde derivatives with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene has been investigated in presence of catalytic quantities of TPPFe^{III}.X and its fluorinated analogues. It was observed that in case of fluorinated catalysts the reaction was indeed facilitated and the Fe^{III}-bound axial anionic ligands play a very important role. The reactions of various substituted benzaldehydes with 2,3-dimethyl butadiene to form the cyclic pyran derivatives have also been studied. The results are indicative of the possible involvement of a polar intermediate in these reactions.

Keywords : Fluorinated iron(III) porphyrins, [4+2] cycloaddition, pyran derivatives, homogeneous catalysis.

Introduction

Metalloporphyrins have been used as catalysts in various organic transformations which are difficult to perform using common metal complexes^{1,2}. The distinct catalytic ability of metalloporphyrins can be attributed to their characteristic structure, in which the tetradentate porphyrin ligand shows rigid in-plane coordination to the metal^{3,4}. The hetero Diels-Alder reaction is one of the most powerful synthetic methods for isolation of six-membered heterocyclic compounds^{5,6}. In particular, the cycloaddition of aldehyde to dienes, which afford the pyran scaffold, has widely been used in the preparation of natural products and physiologically active substances⁷. However, the majority of these reactions involve the use of activated aldehydes such as glyoxalate or electron rich dienes such as Danishefsky's diene and Rawal's diene^{8,9}. Only a limited number of hetero Diels-Alder reactions in which the unactivated aldehydes and simple dienes are employed where some simple TPPFe^{III} complexes are used as catalysts¹⁰. Hence, we thought that porphyrin based iron(III) Lewis acid catalysts could be prepared using porphyrins and weakly coordinating axial ligands, so that the cationic nature of iron(III) may be revealed. Such type complex would preferentially coordinate with a hard Lewis base such as an aldehyde and might chemoselectively ac-

tivate simple dienes, thus compensating for their low reactivity; consequently, [4+2] cycloaddition would proceed efficiently to afford the corresponding pyrans. To test our hypothesis, we have chosen fluorine substituted iron(III) porphyrins as catalysts and have employed them as catalysts in the coupling reactions of a series of aromatic aldehydes with a simple diene in toluene. All the reactions were conducted for 12 h at 90 °C temperature and the results are reported here.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the iron(III) porphyrin catalysts were synthesized according to literature procedure¹¹⁻¹³. Further these TPPFeCl, F₈TPPFeCl, F₁₂TPPFeCl, F₁₆TPPFeCl, F₂₀TPPFeCl (0.1 g) and AgBF₄/AgSbF₆/AgClO₄/AgPF₆ (5 equivalent) were reacted in dry CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml) for 2 h under argon atmosphere and the precipitated AgCl was separated by slow filtration through G-4. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the dried powders were used without further purification to get results for the counter anions.

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker spectrosin DPX-300 NMR spectrometer at 300.13 and 75.47 MHz, respectively using CDCl₃ as a solvent at room tempera-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

ture. Mass spectra (HRMS) were collected in the electrospray ionization (ESI) mode (10 eV, 180 °C source temperature and sodium formate as calibrant) on a Bruker micrOTOF-QII, taking the samples in acetonitrile/methanol. Infrared spectra were recorded on an Agilent Technologies Cary 660 model Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer instrument series II CHNS/O Analyser 2400 model.

Catalytic experiments :

Appropriate iron(III) porphyrin (5 mol %), aldehyde (0.5 mmol), the diene (2 mmol) and dry toluene (1.5 ml) were taken in a screw cap vial and were saturated with argon. The vial was sealed and stirred at 90 ± 2 °C. The reaction mixture was diluted with hexane, passed through a short silica gel column, washed with hexane/ethyl acetate (10/1) and finally concentrated *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by flash column chromatography using basic Al_2O_3 (hexane/ethyl acetate) or SiO_2 (hexane/ethyl acetate/triethylamine).

Results and discussion

The list of catalysts used is given in Scheme 1. The hetero Diels-Alder reactions of benzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene in presence of catalytic quantities of various iron(III) porphyrins ($\text{PFe}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{X}$) were studied in toluene at 90 ± 2 °C under argon atmosphere (Scheme 2). In this study five iron(III) porphyrins with systematic increments of peripheral fluorines on porphyrins are used. In all the catalysts iron(III) bound anions are also varied. This reaction does not proceed without any catalyst. In case of catalyst $\text{PFe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}$ (entry 1, Table 1),

Scheme 1. Structures of the catalysts used for the [4+2] hetero Diels-Alder reaction.

Scheme 2. Hetero Diels-Alder reaction in presence of $\text{PFe}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{X}$ catalysts.

Table 1. Iron(III) porphyrin catalysed [4+2] cycloaddition reaction of benzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene^a

X	The % yield of pyran derivative in presence of various catalysts				
	TPPFe.X	F ₈ TPPFe.X	F ₁₂ TPPFe.X	F ₁₆ TPPFe.X	F ₂₀ TPPFe.X
Cl	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1
PF ₆	25	30	34	40	52
BF ₄	91	92	92	93	94
ClO ₄	72	80	84	85	85
SbF ₆	80	82	84	86	90

^aReactions were carried out using the catalysts (5 mol %), benzaldehyde (0.5 mmol) and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene (2 mmol, 4 equivalent) in 1.5 ml solvent at 90 °C for 12 h. The yields are with reference to benzaldehyde.

the reaction does not proceed much. With the change of anion (X^-) from Cl^- to PF_6^- (entry 2, Table 1), a reasonable improvement in the yield was noted from 1 to 25% in case of simple $\text{TPPFe}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{PF}_6$. The time bound plots for the benzaldehyde and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene [4+2] cycloaddition reaction catalysed by $\text{F}_{20}\text{TPPFe}\cdot\text{PF}_6$ and $\text{TPPFe}\cdot\text{PF}_6$ are shown in Fig. 1 which shows that all the time during the reaction, $\text{F}_{20}\text{TPPFe}\cdot\text{PF}_6$ works superior

Fig. 1. The time bound plot for $\text{F}_{20}\text{TPPFe}\cdot\text{PF}_6$ and $\text{TPPFe}\cdot\text{PF}_6$ catalysed [4+2] cycloaddition of benzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene.

to TPPFe.PF₆. The yields were systematically improved from 25 to 52% when the porphyrins were made more and more electronegative by systematically increasing the number of fluorine atoms on the periphery of porphyrin ligand. Interestingly, when the axial X in PFe^{III}.X was changed to BF₄, ClO₄ and SbF₆, the yields were drastically improved (entry 3–5, Table 1).

In order to have more insight about the reactive intermediates, the TPPFe.X and F₂₀TPPFe.X catalysed cycloaddition reactions of 2-fluorobenzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene in toluene at 90 ± 2 °C (Scheme 3) were studied and the results are given in Table 2. It was observed that the yield of fluorine substituted pyran product was higher even in case of simple TPPFe.PF₆ (entry 2, Table 2). Comparing the product profile of the reaction of benzaldehyde and 2-fluorobenzaldehyde with 2,3-

Scheme 3. TPPFe.X and F₂₀TPPFe.X catalysed cycloaddition reactions of 2-fluorobenzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene in toluene at 90 ± 2 °C.

Table 2. TPPFe.X and F₂₀TPPFe.X catalyzed [4+2] cycloaddition reactions of 2-fluorobenzaldehyde and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene^a

X	TPPFe.X	F ₂₀ TPPFe.X
Cl	<1	<1
PF ₆	90	90
BF ₄	90	95
ClO ₄	80	88
SbF ₆	90	90

^aReactions were carried out using the catalysts (5 mol%), 2-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.5 mmol) and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene (2 mmol, 4 equivalent) in 1.5 ml solvent at 90 °C for 12 h. The yields are with reference to 2-fluorobenzaldehyde.

dimethylbutadiene in presence of F₂₀TPPFe.PF₆, it was observed that 2-fluorobenzaldehyde is more efficient all the time (Fig. 2).

The reactions with benzaldehyde containing variable substituents such as -F, -Cl, -Br, -CH₃, -NO₂ and -CN on the benzene ring were then performed under similar conditions (Scheme 4) and the results are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 2. The time bound plot for the reaction of 2-fluorobenzaldehyde and benzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene catalysed by F₂₀TPPFe.PF₆.

Scheme 4. Reactions of F₂₀TPPFe.X with benzaldehyde containing variable substituents such as -F, -Cl, -Br, -CH₃, -NO₂ and -CN.

Table 3. F₂₀TPPFe.X catalysed [4+2] cycloaddition reaction of substituted benzaldehydes with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene^a

Aldehyde	Pyrans yield (%) in presence of F ₂₀ TPPFe.X with variable X				
	X = Cl	BF ₄	SbF ₆	ClO ₄	PF ₆
Benzaldehyde	<1	94	90	85	52
2-Fluorobenzaldehyde	<1	95	90	88	90
2-Bromobenzaldehyde	<1	94	85	75	58
3-Chlorobenzaldehyde	<1	90	80	68	45
3-Bromobenzaldehyde	<1	90	74	62	36
4-Bromobenzaldehyde	<1	82	70	60	35
4-Methylbenzaldehyde	<1	95	92	78	56
4-Nitrobenzaldehyde	<1	72	68	44	32
4-Cyanobenzaldehyde	<1	64	58	36	26

^aReactions were carried out using the catalyst (5 mol%), benzaldehyde (0.5 mmol) and 2,3-dimethylbutadiene (2 mmol, 4 equivalent) in 1.5 ml solvent at 90 °C for 12 h. The yields are with reference to the aldehydes.

It was observed that 2-fluorobenzaldehyde reacts most efficiently with reference to 2-bromobenzaldehyde while

3-bromobenzaldehyde is less efficient with reference to 2-bromobenzaldehyde. In another case it was observed that 3-chlorobenzaldehyde is more efficient with reference to 3-bromobenzaldehyde. Comparing the reactivity based on inductive effects catalysed by $F_{20}TPPFe.X$, we may conclude that the reactivity orders are $F > Cl > Br$ and 2-bromobenzaldehyde $>$ 3-bromobenzaldehyde $>$ 4-bromobenzaldehyde. The comparative plot for various electronegatively substituted benzaldehydes for [4+2] cycloaddition with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene catalysed by various counter anions of $F_{20}TPPFe.X$ where $X = BF_4, SbF_6, ClO_4$ and PF_6 is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Comparative plot for various substituted benzaldehydes for [4+2] cycloaddition with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene catalysed by $F_{20}TPPFe.X$ where $X = BF_4, SbF_6, ClO_4$ and PF_6 .

In order to understand the electron withdrawing effect and electron donating effect on benzaldehyde for these [4+2] cycloaddition reactions, we compared the product formation for 4-methylbenzaldehyde, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 4-cynobenzaldehyde with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene (Fig. 4). It is observed that 4-methylbenzaldehyde forms the product most efficiently while 4-cynobenzaldehyde is the least reactive.

The results indicate that if electron density is decreased on iron(III) center ($TPPFe.X$ vs $F_{20}TPPFe.X$), the yields are improved. Moreover, on increasing the polarity of $-C=O$ group of aldehyde by putting the electronegative groups at *o*-, *m*- and *p*-positions on the attached benzene ring, the reactivity is increased systematically due to $-I$ effect. On the basis of these results the following most probable reaction pathway is proposed (Scheme 5).

Fig. 4. The comparative plot for electron withdrawing and electron donating substituted benzaldehydes for [4+2] cycloaddition with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene catalysed by various counter anion of $F_{20}TPPFe.X$ where $X = BF_4, SbF_6, ClO_4$ and PF_6 .

Scheme 5. The proposed catalytic cycle for the hetero Diels-Alder reaction of benzaldehyde with simple diene catalysed by iron(III) porphyrin.

The chlorido ligand seems to remain undetached in nonpolar toluene solvent, and with forcible detachment of the halide by Ag^+ , the weakly coordinating BF_4^- , SbF_6^- , ClO_4^- and PF_6^- facilitates the substrate to come close to

iron(III) center and gets activated. In this activation process with respect to ligation ability, the aldehyde is given priority with reference to the diene. The rest of the cycle is indeed speculative but seems to be reasonably rational.

Conclusion

The role of counter anions and substituents on iron(III) porphyrin catalysts for hetero Diels-Alder type [4+2] cycloaddition of unactivated aldehydes with simple dienes has been investigated. The results strongly suggest that the fluorinated cationic iron(III) porphyrins are more effective catalysts. That the lability of the iron(III) bound axial ligand is very important and that the polarity of aldehyde carbonyl bond plays an important role in these reactions, have been established.

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